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by

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The Rediscovery of a Lost Sestertius Type and the Dacian Embassy to the Roman Senate in AD 102¹

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[PLATES 2-5]

THE remains of the ancient Roman and medieval settlement of Ferento² lie about 90 km north of Rome, near the town of Viterbo, in an area which was part of Etruria in antiquity. Since 1994, the Università degli Studi della Tuscia has been carrying out a project to investigate and study the site.³ To date, the excavations have yielded almost 2,000 coins,⁴ spanning the 4th/3rd century BC⁵ to the medieval period. During the 2002 excavation campaign, the following remarkable sestertius of Trajan (AD 98–117) was found as a stray find in a late antique layer (US 1477).

Obv. IMP CAES NERVA TRAIAN AVG – GERM DACICVS P M

Laureate bust of Trajan to the right, in a half-frontal view, with the aegis on his left shoulder.⁶ The aegis prominently features the head of Medusa; both ties of the laurel wreath fall down Trajan's neck.

Rev. TR P [VII IMP IIII COS] IIII [DES] V P P; in exergue, SC

Trajan in military dress stepping right (*balteus* across the chest clearly visible), holding short sceptre in his right hand and extending his left arm.⁷

¹ The authors are grateful to Elisabetta De Minicis, Anna Gruzzi and Sara Carannante (all Università degli Studi della Tuscia, Viterbo) for their cooperation and advice in the preparation of this article, as well as to Michel Amandry (BnF, Paris) and Klaus Vondrovec (Kunsthistorisches Museum, Vienna) for the opportunity to reproduce coins in their respective collections, and to an anonymous referee of this journal for his valuable comments.

² On the different forms of the ancient name of Ferento see J. Gascou, 'Le nom antique de Ferento: Ferentium, Ferentis, Ferenti?', *Epigraphica* 62 (2000), pp. 294–7, and G. Romagnoli, *Ferento e la Teverina viterbese* (Viterbo, 2006), pp. 55–7.

³ G. Maetzke et al., 'Ferento: trasformazioni di un contesto urbano tra tarda antichità e bassomedioevo', in: S. Lusuardi Siena (ed.), *Fonti archeologiche e iconografiche per la storia e la cultura degli insediamenti nell'altomedioevo* (Milan, 2003), pp. 91–122; E. De Minicis et al., 'Ferento nel medioevo. Prime acquisizioni dai nuovi settori di scavo', in: P.A. Gianfrotta – A.M. Moretti (eds), *Archeologia nella Tuscia (Atti dell'Incontro di studio)*. Daidalos 10 (Viterbo, 2010), pp. 241–305.

⁴ The specimens found during the 1993–2003 excavation campaigns were studied by one of the authors (DW) as part of a doctoral dissertation defended at the Università degli Studi di Tor Vergata (Rome) in 2007. The dissertation is currently being revised for publication as a monograph.

⁵ The earliest specimen found is Punic (similar to *SNG Cop.* 107–8). See D. Williams, 'Note sulla circolazione monetaria in Etruria meridionale nel III secolo a.C.', in: N. Holmes (ed.), *ProcINC 14 (Glasgow 2009)* (Glasgow, 2011), pp. 1103–14.

⁶ Bust type 'e' according to B. Woytek, *Die Reichsprägung des Kaisers Traianus (98–117)*. MIR 14, 2 vols (Vienna, 2010), p. 78 and pl. III. For an example of this bust type on sestertii of early AD 103, see, e. g., the illustration on pl. 24, no. 156e.

⁷ Unfortunately, the condition of the coin does not permit one to establish conclusively whether or not Trajan holds a small object – a globe? – in his left hand. For discussion, see below in the text.

On the emperor's right side, a man wearing a cap kneeling to the right, with his arms outstretched. In front of the two, Roma (wearing a helmet) with a short sword on her left side seated left on armour (cuirass, shield), her feet on a stool and probably holding a statuette of Victory in her right hand.⁸

Weight before cleaning 25.05g, after cleaning 25.03g; max. diameter 35mm; die axis 6h.

Università degli Studi della Tuscia, Viterbo (inv. 1714, temporary deposit). **Pl. 2, 1** (uncleaned), **1a** (cleaned) and **1A** (as 1a, 200%).

Mint of Rome, struck in December 102.

Cp. *RIC* 2, Trajan 448 (quoting Cohen, second edition, Trajan 598).

Cp. Strack⁹ Anhang IV, p. 301, no. 55 (no specimen known).

Cp. Woytek, *MIR Traianus* vol. 1, p. 107 (no specimen known).

This variety is unpublished. However, a closely similar variety of the same type, differing from the sestertius presented here only in the attributes of two figures on the reverse, was reported in the numismatic literature of the later 17th century, whence Henri Cohen (1806–1880) cited it; via Cohen, the type entered the second volume of *RIC* (published in 1926). Apparently, not a single numismatic author of the 18th, 19th or early 20th centuries handled such a coin. The importance of the sestertius from Ferento is borne out by the fact that the type also remained unknown to the two scholars subsequently undertaking systematic studies of Trajan's imperial coinage in its entirety, based on the inspection of tens of thousands of pieces, i.e. Paul Strack and one of the authors of this note.

Hence, this intriguing coin warrants further investigation. We will first outline the rather complex literary evidence on the type, then discuss the iconography of the sestertius against the background of similar coin designs of the Early and High Principate, and finally examine the type's context in Trajan's coinage as well as its historical implications.

The reference coin for the piece presented here was first published in 1674 by Jean Foy-Vaillant (1632–1706),¹⁰ in the first edition of his manual on Roman imperial coins, which was to become extremely popular and went through several different printings in various European countries in the 17th and 18th centuries.¹¹ For scholarly

⁸ This seems to be the most plausible possibility, in view of the images of the seated Roma on other Trajanic reverses: she holds a statuette of Victory on *MIR Traianus* nos 29, 30, 59, 77, 108, 109–1, 281 and 332–4. The only other attribute in her right hand attested on Trajanic coins is a wreath: *MIR Traianus* nos 109–2, 3. The *palladium* is not featured as an attribute under Trajan.

⁹ P.L. Strack, *Untersuchungen zur römischen Reichsprägung des zweiten Jahrhunderts. Teil I: Die Reichsprägung zur Zeit des Traian* (Stuttgart, 1931).

¹⁰ On him, see C. Dekesel, 'Jean Foy-Vaillant (1632–1706): l'antiquaire du roy', in C. Dekesel – Th. Stäcker (eds), *Europäische numismatische Literatur im 17. Jahrhundert*. Wolfenbütteler Arbeiten zur Barockforschung 42 (Wiesbaden, 2005), pp. 69–87. The problem of this numismatist's name is treated by Dekesel p. 69; he was born as 'Foy' and published some of his works under the name 'Vaillant', others under the name 'Foy-Vaillant'.

¹¹ For the editions of the 17th century, all of which have two volumes, see Dekesel, 'Foy-Vaillant', pp. 74f.

purposes, the first edition of this work is particularly valuable in that it contains references to collections for all of the pieces cited, references which were for the most part omitted in subsequent editions, as has been pointed out by Wilhelm Kubitschek.¹² The entry for the sestertius in the first edition of Vaillant's work¹³ runs as follows: 'TR. P. VIII. IMP. IIII. COS. IIII. DES. V. Imperator paludatus insidens trophaeo, dextra hastam gerens, ante quem alia figura paludata genuflexa, tertia stans assistit.' '*Hic nummus, primæ formæ, musei Sangenovæfœi, rarissimus habetur*'. The entry is marked with an asterisk *in margine*, indicating that the type had been unknown to Adolph Occo,¹⁴ who published the second edition of his epoch-making monograph on Roman imperial coins in 1601.¹⁵ In Vaillant's catalogue, special prominence is accorded to this piece insofar as it is the only large bronze of Trajan to be illustrated, with both obverse and reverse being depicted on a copperplate on p. 46 (**Pl. 3, 2**).¹⁶ On this engraving, the obverse legend of the piece reads IMP. CAES. NERVA. TRAIAN. AVG. – GERM. DACICVS. P. M., whereas the reverse legend is TR. P. VII. IMP. IIII. COS. IIII. DES. V. (with S.C. in the exergue). The number of the TR P thus differs between Vaillant's illustration and his description; it is wrong in the text, but correct in the image,¹⁷ which may indicate that the copperplate was produced after a not too inaccurate drawing of the actual coin. Comparison between Vaillant's illustration and his descriptive text reveals additional discrepancies: the helmeted figure on the right, seated on arms, is clearly Roma, and cannot be the emperor, as surmised by Vaillant; furthermore, the image shows a spear in the hand of the standing figure, not of the figure seated on a 'trophy' (that is, on pieces of armour) on the right. It seems that Vaillant penned the text of his monograph quite carelessly.

In the following 17th-century editions of Vaillant's catalogue, the illustration created for the 1674 printing was replaced by a close copy, hardly distinguishable from the original (**Pl. 3, 3**),¹⁸ the transcription of the reverse legend was adapted (and corrected as far as the number is concerned), but the incorrect description of

¹² W. Kubitschek, 'Die Erstauflage von Vaillants Numismata Imp. Rom. Præstantiora (1674)', *Numismatik. Internationale Monatsschrift* 1 (no. 1, April 1932), pp. 4–8, esp. pp. 4f.

¹³ I. Vaillant, *Numismata Imperatorum Romanorum Præstantiora. A Iulio Cæsare ad Postumum et Tyrannos*, 2 vols (Paris: R. de Ninville – I. Villery, 1674). Vol. 1: *De Romanis Æreis seu Senatusconsulto Percussis*, p. 51. There is a re-issue of this first edition with an adapted title page (Paris: Th. Moette, 1682): see Dekesel, 'Foy-Vaillant' pp. 74f. (calling it 'seconde édition').

¹⁴ See Vaillant, *Numismata Imperatorum* (1674), vol. 1, præfatio, unpaginated, fol. [a iiii] r.

¹⁵ *Imp. Romanorum Numismata a Pompeio Magno ad Heraclium editio altera, Multis nummorum milibus aucta* (Augustae Vindelicorum, 1601). The third edition of this work, edited by Francesco Mezzabarba Birago, appeared in print only after the first edition of Vaillant's book, in 1683.

¹⁶ For Vaillant's illustration policy, see his præfatio in vol. 1, fol. [a iiii] r.–v.: '*quemlibet Imperatorem, Caesarem, & Augustam elegantiori aut nondum incita* [sic, lege: *incisa*] *icone illustrantes*'.

¹⁷ Trajan's TR P VIII is never mentioned on his coins, while TR P VI and VII do occur and were current during the final phase of Trajan's fourth consulship (COS IIII DES V): see Woytek, *MIR Traianus*, vol. 2, p. 601. When he assumed the *cognomen ex virtute* 'Dacicus', the titlature already read TR P VII: Woytek, *MIR Traianus* 'Supplementgruppe 3' (to group 6).

¹⁸ It differs only in minor details; perhaps the most significant of them is that the new version does not show a break in the obverse legend. The break AVG – GERM in the original engraving nicely corresponds to the break on the Ferento sestertius presented here.

the coin type was left unchanged.¹⁹ The last of the numerous editions of this work on Roman imperial coins was the so-called ‘*Editio prima Romana*’ published in Rome in 1743, for the first time in three (instead of two) volumes. It was adorned with new engravings in a completely different style and became the most wide-spread edition of Vaillant’s work.²⁰ Here, the Trajanic sestertius with the emperor, Roma and a kneeling figure is still the only large bronze of this emperor to be depicted.²¹ The new illustration differs markedly from the copperplates in the previous editions (Pl. 3, 4); its quality is somewhat inferior and it seems safe to assume that the image was produced by simply copying the other illustrations available. The misleading descriptive text was, again, left substantially unchanged in the Roman edition and does not contain an indication of the coin’s location.²²

In the first edition, Vaillant cited the coin from the *Museum Sangenovæfæi*, i.e. the coin collection of the ‘Bibliothèque de Sainte Geneviève’ in Paris. The sestertius is indeed described in the numismatic section of the celebrated book on the treasures of this library’s *Wunderkammer*, by Claude du Molinet (1620–1687), published posthumously.²³ It is featured among the ‘*médailles les plus rares de grand bronze*’ of the collection; only its reverse is illustrated on plate 19, no. V (Pl. 3, 5). Du Molinet seems to have been the first to elaborate on the Dacian context of the type; still, he retained Vaillant’s patently erroneous identification of the figures depicted standing and seated on the reverse: ‘On voit sur cette Médaille une figure d’un soldat, qui presente à l’Empereur Trajan assis sur un trophée d’armes, un homme à genoux, & en état de suppliant; c’est assurément Decebal Roy des Daces, que Trajan avoit subjugué: ce Roy luy fait hommage comme à son vainqueur, & implore sa clemence. Dion en parle en ces termes: *Ad Trajanum deductus Decebalus humi procumbens eum suppliciter adoravit*. L’inscription qui est à l’entour, nous marque

¹⁹ See, for example, the third edition (‘*Editio tertia emendatior & plurimis rarissimis nummis auctior*’): I. Vaillant, *Numismata Imperatorum Romanorum Præstantiora a Julio Cæsare ad Postumum et Tyrannos*, 2 vols (Amsterdam: Gallet, 1696). Vol. 1: *De Romanis Æreis, seu Senatus Consulto percussis* [...]. *Cui accessit series Numismatum Maximi Moduli*, p. 46 (illustration) and p. 51 (text, where the legend is given as ‘TR. POT. VII. IMP. IIII. COS. IIII. DES. V.’). The reference to the source is omitted, as mentioned above.

²⁰ See the positive judgement on this edition by I. Eckhel, *Doctrina numorum veterum*, vol. 1: *continens prolegomena generalia, tum numos Hispaniae, Galliae, Britanniae, Germaniae, Italiae cum insulis* (Vienna, 1792), p. CLVI.

²¹ J. Vaillant, *Numismata Imperatorum Romanorum Præstantiora a Julio Cæsare ad Postumum usque*. [...] Vol. 1: *De Romanis Æreis S.C. percussis. Editio Prima Romana Plurimis rarissimis Nummis aucta. Cui accessit Appendix A Postumo ad Constantinum Magnum* (Rome, 1743), p. 47 (for the description, see p. 52).

²² ‘TR. POT. VII. IMP. IIII. COS. IIII. DES. V. Imperator paludatus insidens trophaeo, dextra hastam gerens, ante quem alia figura paludata genuflexa, tertia stans adsistit. *Hic nummus primæ formæ rarissimus habetur*’.

²³ C. Du Molinet, *Le cabinet de la Bibliothèque de Sainte Geneviève. Divisé en deux Parties. Contenant les Antiquitez de la Religion des Chrétiens, des Egyptiens, & des Romains; des Tombeaux, des Poids & des Médailles; des Monnoyes, des Pierres antiques gravées, & des Mineraux; des Talismans, des Lampes antiques, des Animaux les plus rares & les plus singuliers, des Coquilles les plus considérables, des Fruits étrangers, & quelques Plantes exquisés* (Paris, 1692).

le temps auquel cette action s'est passée'.²⁴ Unfortunately, it is impossible to check this sestertius today: the collections of the Bibliothèque Sainte-Geneviève did not survive the French Revolution intact. The coins and medals were transferred to the Cabinet des médailles of the Bibliothèque nationale in May 1793.²⁵ Despite reports that this part of the collection was moved in its entirety,²⁶ at least some pieces seem to have been dispersed: in any case, the sestertius in question is not part of the French national collection today.²⁷

In volume six of the *Doctrina numorum veterum*, Joseph Eckhel cited this coin type from Vaillant, but sensibly revised the descriptions given in the above-mentioned 17th-century catalogues according to the evidence provided by Vaillant's illustration. Eckhel correctly identified the emperor and the city goddess; he interpreted the kneeling figure as a personification of Dacia.²⁸ When Henri Cohen listed this coin type in volume two of his *Description historique*, his only authority was still 'Vaillant': apparently, the type had not been encountered in the meantime. Unlike Eckhel, Cohen tacitly added 'P P' at the end of the coin's reverse legend, since all other dated legends of Trajan from AD 99 onwards end with that title. He followed the Viennese 'Father of Numismatics' in the description of the reverse (without citing the *Doctrina*, however).²⁹ Mattingly and Sydenham, for their part, translated a short version of Cohen's description into English for *RIC*, but preferred to identify the kneeling person as a Dacian.³⁰ This interpretation was doubtless occasioned by the occurrence of many similar images of kneeling Dacians begging for mercy on other imperial coin types of Trajan.³¹

²⁴ Du Molinet, *Le cabinet de la Bibliothèque de Sainte Geneviève*, p. 70. Ibid. the reverse inscription is transcribed as TR. POT. VIII. IMP. IIII. COS. IIII. DES. V., while in the illustration on plate 19, it is TR. P. VIII. IMP. IIII. COS. IIII. DES. V (with SC in the exergue); there, the obverse legend is given as IMP. CAES. NERVA. TRAIAN. AVG. GER. DACICVS. P. M.

²⁵ See the detailed account in N. Petit – F. Zehnacker, *Le cabinet de curiosités de la Bibliothèque Sainte-Geneviève: Des origines à nos jours*. Catalogue of the exhibition in Paris, 21 August – 30 September 1989 (Paris, 1989), pp. 15, 69 and 137. Cp. also J.-B. Giard, *Bibliothèque nationale. Catalogue des monnaies de l'Empire romain*, vol. 1: *Auguste* (Paris, second ed. 1988), p. VII, note 6, and Th. Sarmant, *La République des médailles. Numismates et collections numismatiques à Paris du Grand Siècle au Siècle des Lumières* (Paris, 2003), p. 336.

²⁶ Petit – Zehnacker, *Le cabinet de curiosités* p. 137.

²⁷ P.-A. Besombes, [Bibliothèque nationale de France.] *Monnaies de l'Empire romain IV. Trajan (98–117 après J.-C.)* (Paris/Strasbourg, 2008). To be used in conjunction with the review article (*inter alia* containing a supplement) by one of the authors of this paper (BEW): 'Trajan dans les collections de la BnF', *RN* 165 (2009), pp. 427–41.

²⁸ I. Eckhel, *Doctrina numorum veterum*, vol. 6: *continens numos imperatorios a Iulio Caesare usque ad Hadrianum eiusque familiam* (Vienna, 1796), p. 415: 'Roma galeata thoraci insidens dexteram extendit versus Daciam genu flectentem, adstat imperator paludatus s. hastam tenens.' For an earlier correct identification of Roma and Trajan, see R. Fabretti, *De Columna Traiani Syntagma* [...] (Rome, 1690), p. 275, where the coin is also cited from Vaillant, in chapter IX ('Numismata occasione utriusque expeditionis in Dacos percussa, & ad eorum intellectum, series chronologica totius Belli Dacici exposita').

²⁹ Cohen, first edition (1859), p. 85, no. 539: 'TR. P. VII. IMP. IIII. COS IIII. DES. V. P. P. Rome casquée assise à gauche sur une cuirasse, tendant la main à la Dacie agenouillée; devant, Trajan debout en habit militaire, tenant une haste.' This description was repeated basically without changes in the second edition (1882), pp. 79f., no. 598.

³⁰ *RIC* 2, p. 276: 'Roma seated l., extending hand to kneeling Dacian; in front, Trajan standing with spear.'

³¹ See, for example, Woytek, *MIR Traianus* nos 220, 247–9, 250–2 etc.

What is the typological relationship between the new sestertius from Ferento and the coin listed by Vaillant and Du Molinet? Although the new coin is in rather poor condition, it is evident from the readily identifiable transverse sceptre in the emperor's right hand, from the position of his left arm and the absence of a vertical spear that the new coin's reverse does not correspond to the 17th century images in every detail. Also, the emperor's bust on the obverse of the Ferento coin shows an aegis, whereas it is undecorated on Vaillant's image. Leaving aside this difference, which is of minor importance due to the fact that obverse dies with different bust types were frequently used simultaneously under Trajan, there are basically two possibilities. The first is that two closely related varieties of the same reverse type, differentiated by the attributes of the figures, were produced in late AD 102, both of which were minted in exiguous quantities,³² so that just one piece each would have come down to us in about 350 years of numismatic research. The second possibility is that the new coin in fact belongs to the very same variety as the sestertius examined by the French scholars in the Early Modern period, but that their illustrations are not reliable – presumably because the specimen in the Bibliothèque Sainte-Geneviève was not well preserved either and the artists responsible for the copperplates were unable to recognize details of the reverse of the coin. Close comparison of the images in Vaillant and Du Molinet shows that the two engravings, although doubtless illustrating the very same coin, differ from each other in several minor points (see **Pl. 3, 2 and 5**). The most obvious difference is the clothing of Roma (whom the two scholars did not recognize as such): while she wears a long garment in Vaillant's image, Du Molinet depicts Roma in Amazonic garb. Since the latter is her standard dress on all the other Trajanic coin types showing the enthroned city-goddess,³³ it is probable that Du Molinet's illustration is trustworthy in this respect. Another difference between the two 17th-century images concerns the number following the letters TR P in the reverse legend – VII and VIII. On balance, it therefore does not seem unreasonable to assume that the reverse of the coin in the Sainte Geneviève collection was ambiguous due to wear, encrustation or corrosion. This might also account for the fact that both Vaillant and Du Molinet simply omitted the P P in the reverse legend.³⁴ Only the reappearance of what was evidently the Sainte Geneviève sestertius, however, would allow us to settle this question with certainty.

Be that as it may, the iconography of the newly found coin's reverse is quite unusual: a three-figure scene with, on the left, a figure kneeling to the right, accompanied by a standing figure behind it and slightly to its right. Structurally, this elaborate composition is somewhat reminiscent of sestertii of Galba and Vespasian with the legends LIBERTAS RESTITVTA and ROMA RESVRGES,³⁵ on which the

³² This would not of course be completely unparalleled in Trajan's bronze coinage: cp. the Roma dupondii *MIR* 109–1 (one specimen known), 109–2 (three specimens), 109–3 (three specimens) as well as X5 (one specimen).

³³ Woytek, *MIR Traianus* nos 29, 30, 59, 77, 108–9, 158, 281, 332–4, X5.

³⁴ Although the inscription on the new coin's reverse is only partly legible, it clearly shows the P P at the end, thus proving that Cohen's emendation was right.

³⁵ F. Schmidt-Dick, *Typenatlas der römischen Reichsprägung von Augustus bis Aemilianus. Zweiter Band: Geographische und männliche Darstellungen* (Vienna, 2011), type I.6.1.02., pp. 25f. (with

emperor raises the personification of Liberty who is accompanied by Roma or Virtus, standing in the background (PI. 4, 6).³⁶

In Trajan's imperial coinage, there are two obvious typological points of reference for our sestertius. The first is the sestertius type *MIR* 158, showing Trajan standing left in the toga, handing over a statue of Victory to the seated city-goddess (PI. 4, 7). These coins, struck in AD 103 (when Trajan had already entered his fifth consulship), doubtless commemorated the emperor's victorious return from the First Dacian War, as comparison with an analogous scene labelled *ADVENTVS AVG* on Hadrianic bronzes shows (PI. 4, 8).³⁷ In view of the re-appearance of the sestertius type under discussion, it may not seem out of place to mention here a variety of *MIR* 158 reported and pictured by Francesco Angeloni (1587–1652) in the mid-17th century (PI. 4, 9),³⁸ which was also illustrated in Pietro Santi Bartoli's magnificent publication of the reliefs of the Column of Trajan (PI. 4, 10).³⁹ A similar coin turned up in the Gréau sale of 1869 (PI. 4, 11),⁴⁰ but no sestertius of this type has since been seen. It basically has the same legends as *MIR* 158⁴¹ and depicts the same scene with Roma and Trajan on the reverse; additionally, a Dacian wearing a cap who is seated

references) and pl. 2. On these coin-types, see the comments by R. Brilliant, *Gesture and Rank in Roman Art. The Use of Gestures to Denote Status in Roman Sculpture and Coinage*. Memoirs of the Connecticut Academy of Arts and Sciences 14 (New Haven, 1963), pp. 87–91.

³⁶ On these and other related Roman imperial coin images, see the study by C.C. Vermeule, 'Un aureo augusteo del magistrato monetario Cossus Lentulus', *Numismatica* 1 (1960), pp. 5–11, reprinted in: C.C. Vermeule, *Art and Archaeology of Antiquity*, vol. 1 (London, 2001), pp. 346–57. It may be mentioned in passing here that a three-figure reverse type with one figure standing on the left (Tyche), one seated on the right (the king) and one in the middle kneeling to the right occurs in Arsacid numismatics: see the tetradrachms of Artabanus II, D. Sellwood, *An Introduction to the Coinage of Parthia* (second ed. London, 1980), nos. 62.1–5.

³⁷ For this interpretation, see already Strack, *Traianus* p. 110. Hadrian's pieces (which duly omit Victory, of course): P.L. Strack, *Untersuchungen zur römischen Reichsprägung des zweiten Jahrhunderts. Teil II: Die Reichsprägung zur Zeit des Hadrian* (Stuttgart, 1933), no. 511 (with p. 58). This type is also known on a large flan: P.F. Mittag, *Römische Medaillons. Caesar bis Hadrian* (Stuttgart, 2010), p. 143, Hadrian no. 3. See also note 64 below.

³⁸ F. Angeloni, *La Historia Augusta da Giulio Cesare insino a Costantino il Magno, illustrata con la verità delle Antiche Medaglie* (Rome, 1641), pp. 110f., no. 14 (illustrated on p. 122); see also: *L'Historia Augusta da Giulio Cesare a Costantino il Magno. Illustrata con la verità dell'Antiche Medaglie da Francesco Angeloni. Seconda Impressione con l'Emendationi Postume del medesimo Autore, e col supplemento de' Rovesci che mancavano nelle loro Tavole, tratti dal Tesoro delle Medaglie della Regina Christina Augusta, e descritti da Gio: Pietro Bellori* (Rome, 1685), p. 98, no. 14 (illustrated on pl. 122, re-used from the first edition). It may be noted that the interpretations of the type offered in the two editions differ from one another.

³⁹ P.S. Bartoli, *Colonna Traiana eretta dal senato, e popolo romano all'imperatore Traiano Augusto nel suo foro in Roma. Scolpita con l'histoire della guerra dacica la prima e la seconda espeditione, e vittoria contro il re Decebalo. Nuovamente disegnata, et intagliata da Pietro Santi Bartoli. Con l'espositione latina d'Alfonso Ciaccone, compendiata nella vulgare lingua sotto ciascuna immagine, accresciuta di medaglie, iscrizioni, e trofei, da Gio. Pietro Bellori* (Rome, n. d. [1672]), pl. 116, no. 28.

⁴⁰ H. Cohen, *Description des médailles romaines composant la collection de M. J. Gréau* (Paris, 1869) [auction catalogue H. Hoffmann, 19 May 1869 and following days], no. 1449 ('Inédite', illustrated on plate III). The coin was bought by Hoffmann himself for 110 Francs, according to the list of prices realized. This piece is cited in Cohen's *Description historique*, where the variety is listed and illustrated (second edition, p. 80, no. 601); *RIC* cites it from Cohen (Trajan no. 453).

⁴¹ On this point see, however, below in the text.

to the left is figured at the emperor's feet.⁴² The authenticity of this variety as being an official product of the Trajanic mint of Rome has been questioned,⁴³ and the fact that the obverse legend of the sestertius reads DACPCVC instead of DACICVS in the illustration provided in the sale catalogue does not indeed at first sight inspire confidence, although admittedly the legend was corrected later when the image was re-used in the second edition of Cohen's *Description historique*.⁴⁴ Thus, one perhaps should not discard this variety too hastily, given the present experience with the specimen from Ferento.

The second and by far the most important typological comparandum for this coin is the aureus type *MIR* 183, struck shortly after the sestertii *MIR* 158, perhaps in AD 103/104 (**Pl. 5, 12–13**).⁴⁵ On these rather uncommon gold coins, Trajan in military dress steps right and presents a kneeling man before him with outstretched hands, who wears trousers and a cap, to a bearded man in a toga holding a scroll. The *togatus*, who should be identified as the *Genius senatus*,⁴⁶ extends his right towards the kneeling Dacian, apparently accepting the foreigner's submission and perhaps offering his hand for a kiss. The gesture of the kneeling man both on the aurei and the new sestertius is well known not only from earlier imperial coins⁴⁷ and later Trajanic issues,⁴⁸ but also from depictions in other media,⁴⁹ most notably from Trajan's column⁵⁰: it is the classic iconography of subservience in Roman art.⁵¹ These aurei have long been interpreted correctly⁵² as referring to a Dacian embassy to the Roman senate after the First Dacian War, which is fortunately mentioned in

⁴² Bellori, *Historia Augusta* (1685), p. 98 had already tentatively identified the figure as 'un prigionie'. The description of Cohen, *Collection de M. J. Gréau* p. 126 does not make sense and seems to be imprecise: 'à ses pieds une captive assise à terre, tenant un globe'. Apparently, Cohen (and Dardel, who produced the illustration) mistook one of the shields on which Roma is seated for a globe; this error goes back to the first edition of Angeloni's book (pp. 110f.), whose illustration also shows a globe.

⁴³ Strack, *Traianus*, p. 301, no. 57 ('moderne Überarbeitung bleibt immer noch möglich').

⁴⁴ Woytek, *MIR Traianus*, vol. 1, p. 264; see Cohen, *Description historique*, second edition, vol. 2 (published in 1882), p. 80.

⁴⁵ The dating suspected by Strack, *Traianus* p. 109 (after the end of the Second Dacian War) is now obsolete; see, most recently, M. Beckmann, 'Trajan's gold coinage dated COS V, AD 103–111', *AJN*² 23 (2011), pp. 169–88, esp. 172 (he confirms the chronology given in *MIR Traianus* for this type).

⁴⁶ *RIC* 2, p. 258, no. 215; Strack, *Traianus*, p. 108.

⁴⁷ Cp., e.g., the typological overview of the pertinent types given by Schmidt-Dick, *Typenatlas*, vol. 2, pls 1–2.

⁴⁸ E.g. *MIR Traianus* nos 220, 247–52 etc. For these types in general, see J. Pinkerneil, *Studien zu den traianischen Dakerdarstellungen* (Dissertation, Freiburg i. Br., 1983), pp. 74–7.

⁴⁹ R.-M. Schneider, *Bunte Barbaren. Orientalenstatuen aus farbigem Marmor in der römischen Repräsentationskunst* (Worms, 1986), *passim*, especially pls 16–9.

⁵⁰ F. Lepper – S. Frere, *Trajan's Column. A New Edition of the Cichorius Plates. Introduction, Commentary and Notes* (Gloucester – Wolfboro, 1988), pp. 116f., notes on scene LXXV (great 'surrender scene' at the end of the First War). See also the comments by N. Hannestad, *Roman Art and Imperial Policy*. Jutland Archaeological Society Publication 19 (Aarhus, 1986), pp. 158–62.

⁵¹ Brilliant, *Gesture and Rank*, *passim*, s. vv. 'submission' and 'supplication', e.g. pp. 70–5, 122–5, 189–95 etc.

⁵² Strack, *Traianus* p. 108; Mattingly, *BMCRE* 3, p. lxxii; Woytek, *MIR Traianus*, vol. 1, p. 113, and B. Woytek, 'Themen der römischen Aureusprägung unter Kaiser Traian: Die Hauptlinien der typologischen Entwicklung', in: S. Deger-Jalkotzy – N. Schindel (eds), *Gold. Tagung anlässlich der*

Cassius Dio (68.9.7–10.1).⁵³ The passage is central to our argument: καὶ πρέσβεις ἐπὶ τούτοις ἐς τὸ βουλευτήριον ἔπεμψεν (sc. ὁ Δεκέβαλος) ὅπως καὶ παρ' ἐκείνου τὴν εἰρήνην βεβαιώσῃται (9.7). [...] καὶ οἱ παρὰ τοῦ Δεκεβάλου πρέσβεις ἐς τὸ συνέδριον ἐσήχθησαν, τὰ τε ὄπλα καταθέντες συνήψαν τὰς χεῖρας ἐν αἰχμαλώτων σχήματι καὶ εἰπόν τέ τινα καὶ ἰκέτευσαν, καὶ οὕτω τὴν τε εἰρήνην ἐσπέισαντο καὶ τὰ ὄπλα ἀπέλαβον (10.1).⁵⁴

This was not the first official visit of Dacian legates to Rome: according to another passage of Dio, envoys of Decebalus had come to the capital after the peace settlement which had concluded Domitian's Dacian war in AD 89.⁵⁵ But it seems that since the days of Augustus, a diplomatic act of this kind had hardly ever been exploited 'propagandistically' like the embassy of AD 102. The visit of the legates, who had presumably accompanied the emperor on his way back from Dacia to the capital,⁵⁶ was, despite the wording in Dio, doubtless orchestrated by Trajan himself and was presented to the public as a major political event.

One of the main reasons for this is evident. The spectacle of Dacian envoys laying down their arms at the heart of the city of Rome, in the Roman *curia*, and proclaiming their submission, before they were formally granted peace by the senate and were allowed to take up their arms again, enabled Trajan to ostentatiously demonstrate his respect and consideration for the Roman senate.⁵⁷ It must be remembered in this context that the ratification, by the senators, of the peace treaty which the emperor had personally concluded in the field with Decebalus would not even have been a constitutional *sine qua non*.⁵⁸

Gründung des Zentrums Archäologie und Altertumswissenschaften an der Österreichischen Akademie der Wissenschaften, 19.–20. April 2007 (Vienna, 2009), pp. 113–36, 120.

⁵³ On the embassy, see A.S. Stefan, *Les guerres daciques de Domitien et de Trajan. Architecture militaire, topographie, images et histoire* (Rome, 2005), p. 625; E. Täubler, *Imperium Romanum. Studien zur Entwicklungsgeschichte des römischen Reichs*. Vol. 1: *Die Staatsverträge und Vertragsverhältnisse* (Leipzig – Berlin, 1913), pp. 185f., and S. Mazzarino, 'I Fasti Ostienses e il primo trionfo dacico di Traiano', *Epigraphica* 40 (1978), pp. 241–6, esp. 242 and 245.

⁵⁴ 'He (sc. Decebalus) also sent envoys in the matter to the senate, in order that he might secure the ratification of the peace by that body.' (9.7) 'The envoys from Decebalus, upon being brought into the senate, laid down their arms, clasped their hands in the attitude of captives, and spoke some words of supplication; thus they obtained peace and received back their arms.' (10.1) (translation E. Cary, Loeb).

⁵⁵ 67.7.3: καὶ ἐς τὴν Ῥώμην ὡς νενικηκῶς ἐπέστειλε τὰ τε ἄλλα καὶ πρέσβεις παρὰ τοῦ Δεκεβάλου (sc. ὁ Δομτιανός): 'And, just as if he had won a victory, he sent to Rome, among other things, envoys from Decebalus'. The purpose of this visit was doubtless the same as in AD 102 – a ratification by the senate of a peace treaty concluded between the emperor and a foreign power in the field. On the Domitianic event and its background, see K. Strobel, *Die Donaukriege Domitians*. Antiquitas Reihe 1, 38 (Bonn, 1989), pp. 89–91, as well as Stefan, *Les guerres daciques*, pp. 425–37. For the role of the senate in foreign relations in the imperial period in general, see F. Millar, 'Emperors, frontiers and foreign relations, 31 B.C. to A.D. 378', *Britannia* 13 (1982), pp. 1–23, esp. 4ff.

⁵⁶ As proposed by J. Dierauer, *Beiträge zu einer kritischen Geschichte Trajans* (Leipzig, 1868), p. 92.

⁵⁷ On this matter, see e.g. P.A. Roche, 'Mixed messages: Trajan and the propaganda of personal status', in C. Deroux (ed.), *Studies in Latin Literature and Roman History. XI*. Collection Latomus 272 (Brussels, 2003), pp. 428–46.

⁵⁸ Thus K. Strobel, *Kaiser Traian. Eine Epoche der Weltgeschichte* (Regensburg, 2010), p. 257. See also Stefan, *Les guerres daciques*, p. 429.

But on a more general note, the aureus reverse and the episode behind it also illustrate a core aspect in the scale of Roman values. The reception of embassies was regarded as a way of affirming Rome's superior international status over foreign peoples:⁵⁹ peace was supposed to be requested by a defeated and frightened enemy, never by Rome. The proper procedure, in Roman eyes, was to reduce an enemy to a submissive state through a military victory and then wait for him to sue for peace.⁶⁰ Hence, it is clear that Domitian's truce with Decebalus was perceived as highly disgraceful (Cass. Dio 67.7.4) – compare also the allusions in Pliny's *Panegyric* (11.5, 12.2).⁶¹ Trajan's war against Dacia was therefore represented as driven by sentiments of retaliation: the monumental trophy at Adamklissi was dedicated to Mars the Avenger.⁶² By emphasising the fact that the Dacian ambassadors had asked for peace in Rome in AD 102, Trajan's government also legitimated *ex post* the vast amount of resources (both human and financial) and the efforts that the Dacian War had demanded. After Trajan had repressed the enemy's *superbia* and avenged *iniuriae* with violence, the ratification of peace by the senate was a consequent step to re-establish and maintain the *decus* of the empire on which the security of each citizen depended.⁶³

Iconographically, the aurei indeed seem to be a direct visual equivalent of Dio's account cited above: the emperor introducing the supplicant, weaponless Dacian to the personification of the Senate who generously treats him with indulgence. From the discovery of the Ferento sestertius, struck at least some months before the gold coins, we learn that the aureus type is the second, somewhat altered, formulation of this graphic concept. Originally, the emperor, returning from the field and so in military dress, was pictured as introducing the Dacian to the city-goddess. These sestertii were produced around the time of Trajan's first triumph, and this may explain why the mint masters chose to picture him with a sceptre. Although it is not at all clear on the new sestertius due to the coin's bad condition, this is probably the triumphator's eagle-tipped sceptre⁶⁴ which is well in evidence, e.g., on sestertii

⁵⁹ On the protocol of Roman diplomacy and the display of power between states, see J. Gagé, 'L'empereur romain et les rois: politique et protocole', *Revue historique* 171 (1959), pp. 1–43, and B. Campbell, 'War and diplomacy: Rome and Parthia, 31 BC – AD 235', in: J. Rich – G. Shipley (eds), *War and Society in the Roman World* (London, 1993), pp. 213–40.

⁶⁰ N.S. Rosenstein, *Imperatores Victi: Military Defeat and Aristocratic Competition in the Middle and Late Republic* (Berkeley, 1990), pp. 133–8.

⁶¹ On Pliny's Domitian, see recently G.O. Hutchinson, 'Politics and the sublime in the Panegyricus', in: P. Roche (ed.), *Pliny's Praise. The Panegyricus in the Roman World* (Cambridge, 2011), pp. 125–41, esp. 128–32.

⁶² K. Strobel, *Untersuchungen zu den Dakerkriegen Trajans* (Bonn, 1984), pp. 34f.; M. Alexandrescu Vianu, 'La propagande impériale aux frontières de l'empire romain. *Tropaeum Traiani*', *Dacia* 60 (2006), pp. 207–34. For the aspect of vengeance, see also Cass. Dio 68.6.1 and 68.9.3.

⁶³ On *decus imperii* and related values, see S. Mattern, *Rome and the Enemy. Imperial Strategy in the Principate* (Berkeley, 1999), pp. 162–210.

⁶⁴ On this sceptre in general, see A. Alföldi, *Die monarchische Repräsentation im römischen Kaiserreiche* (Darmstadt, 1970), pp. 230–2, as well as C. Panella (ed.), *I segni del potere. Realtà e immaginario della sovranità nella Roma imperiale* (Bari, 2011), especially pp. 80–93 (numismatic sources) and 252–4 (comparanda in other media). A parallel depiction of an emperor approaching the seated Roma with an eagle-tipped sceptre in his hand is provided by medallions of Hadrian showing

struck to commemorate the emperor's second Dacian triumph in AD 107 (*MIR* 308: **Pl. 5, 14**). The sceptre is rendered schematically on the latter coins,⁶⁵ but its upper part may be seen to be shaped much like the upper part of the rod-shaped object held by Trajan on the aurei *MIR* 183; hence, Mattingly was doubtless right in describing it as a 'sceptre' here.⁶⁶ On the aurei, this is Trajan's only attribute, whereas on the sestertius, he may also be holding a globe, although the coin's state of preservation precludes certainty.⁶⁷

One of the most exciting aspects of the discovery of the Ferento coin is that it completes the series of bronze denominations featuring the title *Dacicus* in the COS IIII DES V period and thus significantly enhances our understanding of the typological programme of this phase. Two general points can be made. First, the group we are dealing with is tiny. Until the new find, only rare middle bronzes had been attested, a dupondius and an as type, in a total of just eleven specimens.⁶⁸ Second, the group marks a typological overhaul of the bronze coinage, as compared to the immediately preceding small groups, which were dominated by thoroughly conventional images, employed from the beginning of Trajan's reign.⁶⁹

What was the new programme like? The iconography of our group's dupondius reverse (*MIR* 136: **Pl. 5, 15–16**) is unusual and has therefore given rise to diverging descriptions in the past.⁷⁰ Careful analysis of the documentation currently available makes it clear that this image is another precursor of the aurei *MIR* 183, discussed above: the *Genius senatus* is shown standing to the left, accepting the submission of a kneeling Dacian, who wears a peaked cap, trousers and a cloak. Behind the barbarian, there is a large altar (on some specimens clearly decorated with a garland),⁷¹ the significance of which has remained obscure to date. The staggered arrangement of the kneeling Dacian and the altar to some extent parallels the layout of the new sestertius in the same group, with Trajan behind the kneeling man. On a different

the emperor *capite velato* in the toga: Mittag, *Medaillons*, Hadrian nos 45–6 (and the commentary on pp. 68f.).

⁶⁵ This point has in general already been discussed by Alföldi, *Repräsentation* p. 231. For a more naturalistic representation of the (short!) eagle sceptre in Trajan's coinage, see e.g., *MIR* 357–8 and 366–9.

⁶⁶ *BMCRE* 3, p. 65 (on no. 244). The descriptions by Strack, *Traianus* p. 108, and Woytek, *MIR Traianus*, vol. 1, p. 275 ('Lanze') have to be amended accordingly.

⁶⁷ On the globe as an imperial attribute in general, see Alföldi, *Repräsentation* pp. 235–8, as well as Schmidt-Dick, *Typenatlas*, vol. 2, pls 37, 56–7, 71 and 74. On Trajan's other imperial coins, the globe never occurs as an attribute of the emperor as such, but only in rare scenes featuring the emperor and a second figure; in one of these, Trajan is depicted in military dress: *MIR Traianus* 10 (AD 98).

⁶⁸ Woytek, *MIR Traianus*, vol. 1, pp. 254f., nos 136–7.

⁶⁹ *MIR* 132–5: Concordia and Pax seated left on the sestertii; a *numen mixtum* conveying primarily the notion of *securitas* and *abundantia* seated left on crossed *cornuacopiae* on the dupondii. Pax and the *numen mixtum*, however, reappeared very soon, at the beginning of the COS V period: *MIR* 154–5.

⁷⁰ See, for example, Strack, *Traianus* p. 108 with n. 423; Woytek, *MIR Traianus*, vol. 1, pp. 107 and 254f.

⁷¹ This was first recognized by C. Moisil, 'Monetele împăratului Traian referitoare la războaiele cu Dacii și la cucerirea Daciei', *Buletinul Societății Numismatice Române* 24 (1929), pp. 11–38, p. 17 (albeit with a question mark). His interpretation was accepted by P.L. Strack in a review of *BMCRE* 3, where Mattingly had first published the specimen illustrated in our **Pl. 5, 15**: *Gnomon* 13 (1937), pp. 669–80, p. 671.

note, the reverse of the COS V aurei *MIR* 183 may now be seen to be a typological amalgamation of the sestertius and dupondius reverses of this COS IIII DES V-group, combining the representations of the *Genius senatus* (from the dupondii) and the standing emperor (from the sestertii) with the ubiquitous kneeling Dacian into a single image. This COS IIII DES V group's as (*MIR* 137), on the other hand, fittingly features a Victory reverse, traditional for this denomination, but of a particular type: Victory, who is alighting to the left, holding a wreath in her right hand and a trophy in her left arm, steps on a (rather inconspicuous) globe (**Pl. 5, 17**). It is the first occurrence of this Victory type under Trajan, whose mint administration was to re-use it in the subsequent group (*MIR* 159), before it was abandoned for good. This rare type was not a Trajanic creation, but was copied from scarce dupondii from late in Domitian's reign which do not bear a reverse legend apart from the SC (**Pl. 5, 18**).⁷²

Despite Mattingly's suggestion that the image should be interpreted merely as symbolising the Dacian victory of Trajan,⁷³ we believe that there are good grounds for suspecting the presence of another semantic level here, too. The type of a winged goddess alighting on a globe with emblems of victory, which is so important in Roman art, has conclusively been shown to derive from the famous statue of Victory which Octavian brought to Rome from Tarentum to set it up in the *curia Iulia* in 29 BC (Cass. Dio 51.22.1f.).⁷⁴ There, it was probably placed on a column (see **Pl. 5, 19**) right opposite the main entrance at the far end of the building, on the podium where the consuls presided over the senate's meetings.⁷⁵ The statue dominated the *curia* and therefore was of immense ideological importance to the Roman state in the imperial period. It is thus easy to understand why the combination of Victory and the *orbis* became a visual code almost automatically triggering in the viewer the association with the Roman senate. The Trajanic asses *MIR* 137 were struck in the

⁷² *RIC* 2.1, second ed. Domitian 803 (AD 95/96). The type is 'Victoria fl(2,3)A10' in F. Schmidt-Dick, *Typenatlas der römischen Reichsprägung von Augustus bis Aemilianus. Erster Band: Weibliche Darstellungen* (Vienna, 2002), p. 122 and pl. 53.

⁷³ *BMCRE* 3, p. xcvi: 'Victory alighting on a globe perhaps refers definitely to successes in the field. She comes from the field with her glad tidings.'

⁷⁴ T. Hölscher, *Victoria Romana. Archäologische Untersuchungen zur Geschichte und Wesensart der römischen Siegesgöttin von den Anfängen bis zum Ende des 3. Jhs. n. Chr.* (Mainz am Rhein, 1967), pp. 6–17. Augustus probably created the composition by adding (*inter alia*) a globe to the Tarentine statue: see G. Hafner, 'Die Romana Victoria in der Curia Iulia', *Arch. Anz.* 1989, pp. 553–8, as well as A.L. Kuttner, *Dynasty and Empire in the Age of Augustus. The Case of the Boscoreale Cups* (Berkeley – Los Angeles – Oxford, 1995), pp. 15 and 25f. Various Victory types used in the coinage of Octavian/Augustus may derive from the Tarentine statue, although the original attributes which Victory held in her hands remain problematic: see Hölscher, p. 39 and P.V. Hill, *The Monuments of Ancient Rome as Coin Types* (London, 1989), pp. 81f. For the statue's history through the centuries, see the excellent overview by H.A. Pohlsander, 'Victory. The story of a statue', *Historia* 18 (1969), pp. 588–97.

⁷⁵ M. R.-Alföldi, 'Signum Deae. Die kaiserzeitlichen Vorgänger des Reichsapfels', in: M. R.-Alföldi, *Gloria Romanorum. Schriften zur Spätantike. Zum 75. Geburtstag der Verfasserin am 6. Juni 2001 herausgegeben von H. Bellen und H.-M. von Kaenel*. *Historia Einzelschriften* 153 (Stuttgart, 2001), pp. 215–28, esp. 221f. and 226 (floor plan of the *curia*). This seems plausible to us, although it is not universally acknowledged that the statue was placed on a column: see Hafner, 'Romana Victoria', pp. 553f. as well as Pohlsander, 'Story of a statue', p. 591.

same group as the dupondii *MIR* 136, depicting, as described above, a symbolic representation of an important act of state which, according to Cassius Dio, took place right in the *curia* on the *Forum Romanum*. It therefore seems plausible to us that the reverse type of the asses was selected deliberately in order to convey, apart from the general message of celebrating Trajan's victory in Dacia, a specific allusion to the extraordinary ceremony in the *curia*.

Can these considerations also shed new light on the use of the same type under Domitian? Traditionally, it is simply taken to refer to the last Flavian's military successes.⁷⁶ This may be correct, of course, but why should Domitian have revived precisely this specific Victory type, with the globe, so late in his reign?⁷⁷ Is there more to the image? Again, the numismatic context may provide a clue. In the issue to which the Domitianic Victory dupondii belong, there is a marked predominance of architectural types on the sestertii, featuring, *inter alia*, a triumphal arch, the *equus maximus Domitiani* and a three-storey building sometimes referred to as the 'Palace of Domitian'.⁷⁸ Fairly detailed records of Domitian's building activity in Rome are provided both by the Chronographer of 354⁷⁹ and in the Chronicle of St. Jerome.⁸⁰ J.C. Anderson has shown that the information preserved in these sources is generally much more reliable than had previously been thought.⁸¹ As for the reference to construction works at the building of the Senate in both passages, there seems to be conclusive archaeological evidence for significant structural interventions under Domitian, including the detachment of the *curia Iulia* from Caesar's forum and perhaps the *curia*'s rebuilding in its present position.⁸² Another point may be considered here. According to Servius (ad Verg. georg. 3.29), Octavian erected in Rome, after his Egyptian victory, a monument of four bronze columns made from the *rostra* of ships destroyed in the battle of Actium. If Markus Sehlmeier is right, as it seems he is, in identifying this monument with a structure depicted on Octavian's

⁷⁶ For example Hölischer, *Victoria Romana*, p. 19: 'Domitian prägt ihn (sc. the type) am Ende seiner Regierung (96 n. Chr.), um seine Sarmaten-Siege zu verherrlichen.'

⁷⁷ For the history of 'Victory on globe' as an imperial coin type, see Hölischer, *Victoria Romana*, pp. 17–22.

⁷⁸ See *RIC* 2.1 second ed. Domitian 796–800. None of these types bears a descriptive reverse legend.

⁷⁹ p. 146 Mommsen, *Chronica Minora* (MGH, *Auctores antiquissimi* IX, 1): *hoc imp. multae operae publicae fabricatae sunt: atria VII, horrea piperataria ubi modo est basilica Constantiniana et horrea Vespasiani, templum Castorum et Minervae, portam Capenam, gentem Flaviam, Divorum, Iseum et Serapeum, Minervam Chalcidicam, Odium, Minuciam veterem, stadium, et thermas Titianas et Traianas, amphitheatrum usque ad clypea, templum Vespasiani et Titi, Capitolium, senatum, ludos IIII, Palatium, metam sudantem et Panteum.*

⁸⁰ p. 191 Helm (= p. 273 Fotheringham): *Multa opera Romae facta, in quibus Capitolium, Forum transitorium, divorum Porticus, Isium ac Serapium, Stadium, Horrea piperataria, Vespasiani templum, Minerva Chalcidica, Odeum, Forum Trajani, Thermae Trajanae et Titianae, Senatus, Ludus matutinus, Mica aurea, Meta sudans, et Pantheon.*

⁸¹ J.C. Anderson, Jr., 'A topographical tradition in fourth century chronicles: Domitian's building program', *Historia* 32 (1983), pp. 93–105, esp. 105. A general evaluation of this emperor's building activities is also provided by F. Kolb, *Rom. Die Geschichte der Stadt in der Antike* (second ed. Munich, 2002), pp. 375–7 and 701, n. 18.

⁸² Anderson, 'Domitian's building program' p. 101 (with further references).

denarii *RIC* 266 immediately in front of the *curia*,⁸³ this identification confirms the notion of Domitianic works there, since Servius informs us that the monument of columns was transferred to the Capitol under Domitian.⁸⁴ This measure would have been necessary if Domitian changed the lay-out of the area. Perhaps his works were subtly alluded to in the imperial coinage through a depiction of the Senate's symbol *par excellence*, the Victory on a globe.

Returning to the Trajanic DACICVS COS IIII DES V bronzes of the end of 102, it seems to us that the one iconographic element of the issue hitherto completely unexplained, the large altar illustrated in the background of the reverse on the dupondii *MIR* 136, can perhaps also be put into context. The scene on these coins is a symbolic version of the Dacian ambassadors' submission in the Roman *curia*: might not the altar be the only important altar in the *curia* which we know about – the altar of Victory (*ara Victoriae*)?

According to information preserved in Roman calendars, this altar was dedicated by Octavian on 28 August of an uncertain year – perhaps already in 29 BC, when both the *curia Iulia* and the statue of Victory were also dedicated.⁸⁵ At the altar of Victory, which was presumably located near the entrance of the *curia*,⁸⁶ senators customarily burnt an offering of incense and made a libation of wine upon their arrival for meetings of the senate.⁸⁷ As is well known, the altar became the subject of controversy in the second half of the fourth century AD, when the emergence of Christianity as Rome's state religion subverted the traditional order, and the altar was finally removed.⁸⁸ Unfortunately, the altar is not depicted very clearly on the few coin images available, where it is partly hidden by the kneeling Dacian; it has an upper cornice and is rather unspecifically decorated with ties and a garland. There is

⁸³ M. Sehlmeier, 'Die Siegesmonumente Octavians nach Actium. Zur Lokalisierung des bronzenen Viersäulendenkmals (Serv. georg. 3,29)', in: J. Spielvogel (ed.), *Res publica reperta. Zur Verfassung und Gesellschaft der römischen Republik und des frühen Prinzipats. Festschrift für Jochen Bleicken zum 75. Geburtstag* (Stuttgart, 2002), pp. 216–26.

⁸⁴ Serv. georg. 3.29: *Augustus ... multa de navali certamine sustulit rostra, quibus conflatis quattuor effecit columnas, quae postea a Domitiano in Capitolio sunt locatae, quas hodieque conspicimus.*

⁸⁵ Thus Hölscher, *Victoria Romana* p. 7, as well as J. Bleicken, *Augustus. Eine Biographie* (third ed. Berlin, 1999), p. 380.

⁸⁶ R.-Alföldi, 'Signum Deae' p. 221, with reference to the valuable indications given by Herodian 7.11.3. This view – shared by, among others, Charles Picard and Giuseppe Ricciotti (see the compendium of views in Pohlsander, 'Story of a statue', pp. 591f.) – though doubted by Pohlsander, seems convincing to us.

⁸⁷ Herodian 5.5.7. The practice was introduced by Augustus, see Suet. Aug. 35.3 and Cass. Dio 54.30.1. When the Dacian legates were received in the *curia* in AD 102, oaths may have been taken in connexion with the ratification of the peace treaty (see Mazzarino, 'I *Fasti Ostienses*', p. 245, n. 14: 'giuramenti rituali sacri') – perhaps at the *ara Victoriae*?

⁸⁸ On the controversy, see A. Demandt, *Die Spätantike. Römische Geschichte von Diocletian bis Justinian 284–565 n. Chr.* Handbuch der Altertumswissenschaft III.6 (Munich, 1989), pp. 130, 134–5, and esp. 425; S. Muth, 'Rom in der Spätantike – die Stadt als Erinnerungslandschaft', in: E. Stein-Hölkeskamp – K.-J. Hölkeskamp (eds), *Erinnerungsorte der Antike. Die römische Welt* (Munich, 2006), pp. 438–56, 455; R. Klein, *Der Streit um den Victoriaaltar. Die dritte Relatio des Symmachus und die Briefe 17, 18 und 57 des Bischofs Ambrosius von Mailand. Einführung, Text und Erläuterungen.* Texte zur Forschung 7 (Darmstadt, 1972).

nothing to exclude its identity with the one surviving depiction of the *ara Victoriae*⁸⁹ in another medium. A frequently illustrated Augustan glass paste gem⁹⁰ of high ideological significance (Pl. 5, 20) shows two Parthians presenting Roman standards to the statue of Victory alighting on a globe, carrying a wreath and a *tropaeum*. Beneath the statue, there is an altar decorated with two heads of Ammon on the sides and the image of Victory in a chariot – doubtless the *ara Victoriae* in the *curia*, as recognized by E. Zwierlein-Diehl.⁹¹ As she correctly pointed out, the statue does not rest on the altar, but the latter probably conceals the column on which the Victory on globe was placed (see Pl. 5, 19). Since the altar and the statue of Victory did not stand side by side in the *curia*, as mentioned above, the composition of the gem must be explained by artistic freedom – the two most prestigious objects of the *curia*, symbolic of the Roman senate's power, both associated with Victory, were simply pictured together.

To sum up: the discovery of the new sestertius provides welcome confirmation of the existence of a coin-type which was first described in the 17th century and whose re-emergence was, despite some critical statements in the literature,⁹² tentatively anticipated by one of the authors of this contribution three years ago.⁹³ It expands our knowledge of a small group of typologically innovative (and influential) Trajanic bronzes which were struck around the time of Trajan's first Dacian triumph, in late AD 102. The coin type shows a complex scene, almost a 'state relief *en miniature*', featuring one of the earliest depictions of a kneeling Dacian on a Trajanic coin; the man is presented to the city-goddess Roma by the emperor. Thus, the scene refers to the Dacian embassy to the Roman senate after the First War, attested in Cassius Dio – a key event for the understanding of Trajan's imperial ideology. In all probability, the as and dupondius of the same issue depict the two most famous architectural elements of the *curia*'s interior, where the meeting described by Dio occurred: the statue of Victory on globe and the *ara Victoriae*.

⁸⁹ There is no literary evidence for it: Pohlsander, 'Story of a statue' p. 591.

⁹⁰ See, for example, A. Furtwängler, *Die antiken Gemmen. Geschichte der Steinschneidekunst im klassischen Altertum*, 3 vols (Leipzig – Berlin, 1900), vol. 1, pl. 37, no. 25 (description vol. 2, p. 178); G. Lippold, *Gemmen und Kameen des Altertums und der Neuzeit* (Stuttgart, n. d.), pl. 33, no. 2 (text on p. 172); Hölscher, *Victoria Romana*, pl. 1, 13; P. Zanker, *Augustus und die Macht der Bilder* (Munich, 1987), p. 191, no. 147; R.M. Schneider, 'Die Faszination des Feindes. Bilder der Parther und des Orients in Rom', in: J. Wiesehöfer (ed.), *Das Partherreich und seine Zeugnisse. Beiträge des internationalen Colloquiums, Eutin (27.–30. Juni 1996)*. *Historia Einzelschriften* 122 (Stuttgart, 1998), pp. 95–127, pp. 104f. and pl. 2,2.

⁹¹ E. Zwierlein-Diehl, *Antike Gemmen und ihr Nachleben* (Berlin – New York, 2007), pp. 129f. and pl. 111, no. 513. It may be remarked that it would have been more or less impossible to render on the coin the details of the altar's decoration as seen on the glass paste gem.

⁹² Both Strack (*Traianus* p. 301, no. 55) and Mattingly (*BMCRE* 3, p. 158, note †) had regarded the type reported by Vaillant as 'very doubtful'.

⁹³ Woytek, *MIR Traianus*, vol. 1, p. 107.

List of illustrations on Plates 2-5

- 1 Trajan, sestertius, Rome, December AD 102, unpublished. Università degli Studi della Tuscia, Viterbo (temporary deposit). See text for details. Uncleaned state.
- 1a As 1, after cleaning.
- 1A As 1a, 200%.
- 2 Vaillant, *Numismata Imperatorum Romanorum Præstantiora* (first ed., 1674), vol. 1, p. 46.
- 3 Vaillant, *Numismata Imperatorum Romanorum Præstantiora. Editio tertia* (1696), vol. 1, p. 46.
- 4 Vaillant, *Numismata Imperatorum Romanorum Præstantiora. Editio Prima Romana* (1743), vol. 1, p. 47.
- 5 Du Molinet, *Le cabinet de la Bibliothèque de Sainte Geneviève* (1692), pl. 19, no. V.
- 6 Vespasian, sestertius, Rome, AD 71, *RIC* (second ed.) Vespasian 195: *Numismatica Ars Classica* 25 (25 June 2003), no. 410 (26.83g).
- 7 Trajan, sestertius, Rome, AD 103, *MIR* 158b: Kunsthistorisches Museum Vienna, inv. no. MK RO 8247 (27.24g).
- 8 Hadrian, sestertius, Rome, AD 118, *RIC* 547: Santamaria 7 March 1910 (Hartwig), no. 1356.
- 9 Angeloni, *La Historia Augusta* (1641), p. 122, no. 14.
- 10 Bartoli, *Colonna Traiana* ([1672]), pl. 116, no. 28.
- 11 Cohen, *Collection de M. J. Gréau* (1869), pl. III, no. 1449.
- 12 Trajan, aureus, Rome, c. AD 103/104, *MIR* 183a: *BMCRE* 3, Trajan no. 244 (7.24g).
- 13 Trajan, aureus, Rome, c. AD 103/104, *MIR* 183b: Paris, Bibliothèque nationale, Besombes no. 192 (7.23g).
- 14 Trajan, sestertius, Rome, c. AD 107/108, *MIR* 308t+: Paris, Bibliothèque nationale, Besombes no. 310 (23.42g).
- 15 Trajan, dupondius, Rome, December AD 102, *MIR* 136e: *BMCRE* 3 pl. 27,7 (Stefano Johnson coll.).
- 16 Trajan, dupondius, Rome, December AD 102, *MIR* 136e: Kunsthistorisches Museum Vienna, inv. no. MK RO 8240 (14.30g).
- 17 Trajan, as, Rome, December AD 102, *MIR* 137c: Florence, Manuscript BMAF 7.2., no. 1631 (11.33g).
- 18 Domitian, dupondius, Rome, AD 95/96, *RIC* (second ed.) Domitian 803: Freeman & Sear Manhattan Sale 1 (5 January 2010), no. 238 (12.35g).
- 19 Commodus, sestertius, Rome, AD 192, *RIC* 613: Glendining's 16 November 1950 (Platt Hall, Part 2), no. 1621.
- 20 Augustan glass paste gem, formerly Northampton collection. Reproduced from Zwierlein-Diehl, *Antike Gemmen und ihr Nachleben*, pl. 111, no. 513 (see *ibid.*, pp. 421f., on no. 513, where the two gems known from the same mould are distinguished). Size: 2.46 x 1.86 cm.

PLATE 2

WILLIAMS and WOYTEK, THE REDISCOVERY OF A LOST SESTERTIUS TYPE (1)

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PLATE 4

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